

Title: Power of Cognitive Computing

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INTRODUCTION:

In the disruptive era of Artificial Intelligence, business processes and entities are changing dramatically. Cognitive Computing appears to be the most important aspect of AI. We shall try to understand the Cognitive computing and its vast applications in Industries. Face recognition, object recognition, speech to text and chatbots are few of popular cognitive services that are used in various businesses for multiple reasons. We shall discuss methods and applications of Cognitive Computing and Services..

AIM:

To highlight Cognitive Computing and its broad categories, its techniques and its powerful applications in Industries and to Share case studies on Cognitive computing in Retail and Telecom Sector

KEYWORDS:

Cognitive Computing, Face Detection, Speech to Text, Artificial Intelligence, Retail Analytics

BIOGRAPHY:

Navin Manaswi has been mentoring AI companies and delivering Data Science Projects for many years in various parts of world. He has worked for Fortune 100 company, Dubai-Smart City Project and Consulting companies. He was recognized as one of top 10 data scientists by a magazine.He has been quite passionate about latest AI research including deep learning algorithms, cognitive computing and blockchain. Soon he is going to launch a book on Cognitive Computing and Deep Learning with globally renowned publication.